

New Uzbekistan's Foreign Policy: From Strategic Partnerships to Regional Leadership after Independence

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Abstract

This research paper explores after independence Uzbekistan what kind of innovations did under 2 president's control, focusing on the foreign countries how and what kind of contracts did in 30 years. Under Islam Karimov's control overall policy and strategic relations developed radically. Under Mirziyoyev's control foreign policy and international relations strengthened and controlled much more open with education and programs. The achievement of independence by each country opens a new page in its history. For Uzbekistan 1991 year of openness to the world, this day changed everybody's life in a different way and opened new opportunities for the country. In the early years of independence, caution was the priority in the country's foreign policy, and ensuring internal stability was the main goal. Under the leadership of Islam Karimov, Uzbekistan began to find its place in the international community, established diplomatic relations with countries around the world, and joined international organizations. During Karimov's time, Uzbekistan became a member of the UN and other international organizations, established diplomatic relations with foreign countries, and opened the way for foreign trips and international economic cooperation. Later, a cautious foreign policy was pursued, prioritizing internal stability. Since 2016, under the leadership of Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the foreign policy vector has fundamentally changed, borders have been opened, and historic steps have been taken to restore an atmosphere of trust with neighboring countries. Regional integration, diplomatic activity, and multi-vector cooperation have increased Uzbekistan's prestige in the international arena and created new opportunities for economic and political development. During the years of independence, Uzbekistan independently formed its foreign policy, setting national interests as a priority. During this period, the country expanded international relations on the basis of strategic cooperation and paid attention to economic and cultural integration. In the field of tourism, a country that had been closed for many years, the simplification of the visa procedure, the increase in the number of international flights and the creation of the "Silk Road" tourism corridors not only increased the flow of tourists, but also strengthened regional cooperation. This developed as an important part of foreign policy and served to form a positive image of Uzbekistan in the international arena. The concept of "soft power" was put into practice through the cultural heritage monuments of historical cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva. Thus, during the years of independence, Uzbekistan took a step from strategic cooperation to regional leadership in foreign policy.

Keywords: *Karimov era foreign policy, Mirziyoyev foreign policy reforms, 1990s Uzbek foreign relations, foreign relationship through education, economic relationship.*

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Introduction

During the end of the Cold War and the emergence of the "new world order," Uzbekistan gained its independence. Great countries and the world community rediscovered Central Asia, with its distinctive

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features and a hub for the once-great Silk Road. But in the last three decades, a lot has happened, and a lot has been written on the dynamics of regional great power competition. Uzbekistan, which gained independence in 1991, has set the protection of sovereignty as the top priority in shaping its foreign policy. Under Islam Karimov, this principle was expressed in practice through cautious diplomacy and a “multi-vector” strategy. One of the first nations to recognize Uzbekistan's independence and establish diplomatic ties was the United States. The United States has shown a regional attitude to Central Asian nations since its early years of independence. promoted the Silk Road Strategy Act (1999) and the Freedom Support Act (1992). American scholars viewed and classified Uzbekistan as an essential nation of the area. Overall, Uzbekistan-US relations were so strong that some analysts viewed this development in Uzbekistan's foreign policy as pro-American. I researched many resources which Usa with Uzbekistan did a lot international relations since 1992. After this Uzbekistan step by step attended global programs to provide peace and development for the country. Taken the GUAM organization, established in 1997, initially emerged as a consultative forum among four countries: Georgia, Ukraine, Azerbaijan, and Moldova. In 1999, Uzbekistan's accession to this organization led to the name change to GUUAM. Uzbekistan's accession to GUAM indicates the Central Asian nation's aspiration to closely cooperate with the Caucasus and Black Sea region. At this stage, the GUUAM organization set goals to promote democratic values, enhance security, and strengthen economic ties. However, starting from 2002, Uzbekistan began to diminish its participation in the organization's activities and officially left in 2005. In my personal analysis, this decision may be closely linked to Uzbekistan's pursuit of balance in its foreign policy and the internal political situation (for example, the Andijan events of 2005). Uzbekistan's short-term membership in GUAM. During this time, according to the author, Uzbekistan's accession to GUAM can be explained by several factors: the desire to pursue an independent foreign policy relative to Russia, the development of economic cooperation with the Caucasus-Black Sea region, participation in transport and energy projects, and the aspiration to strengthen political ties with Western countries, particularly the USA (Aliyev, 2005). However, starting from 2002, Uzbekistan ceased to participate in GUAM events and officially withdrew from the organization in 2005. This led to the organization reverting back to its name GUAM. The GUAM organization obtained observer status in the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) in 2003. Through this, it strengthened its international recognition and gained the opportunity to elevate regional issues to a global level (UNGA, 2003). Notably, Uzbekistan was admitted to the UN as a full member on March 2, 1992. During the first president Islam Karimov's era Uzbekistan pursued a multi-vector foreign policy, aiming to maintain a balance between Russia, China, and Western countries. The main aim of Karimov's policy was to

transform the country into an independent and self-sufficient state, favoring caution and conservatism in foreign relations. To maintain his political stability, he strengthened both internal and external security and actively participated in the fight against regional terrorism. At the same time, a centralized role of the state in economic policy was preserved, and there were restrictions on attracting foreign investments (Freinkman et al., 2015). After 2016, this approach underwent significant changes under Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Based on the concept of “New Uzbekistan”, foreign policy took on an active, open and regionally oriented form. Shavkat Mirziyoyev's presidency openly showed for everyone. When it comes to countries, especially with USA, during the first president it was much more close but then it is changed significantly: specifically with education and development. Shavkat Mirziyoyev did a contract with a lot developed countries for students who are eager to study. Not only with the USA but also with China, Korea, Europe, Turkey and Russia. A lot of students take higher education in these countries and help their countries develop after taking their degree. Through this Shavkat Mirziyoyev provided the development of Uzbekistan. Collaboration with the USA is based on English language, pedagogy, scientific research, and technological innovations. Through programs like "Fulbright" and "Global UGRAD", Uzbek students and teachers are gaining qualifications in the USA and bringing their experiences back to the homeland (UzSWLU, 2023). At the same time, seminars and training conducted with the support of the US Embassy and the British Council are modernizing language teaching methodologies. Collaboration with China is primarily focused on language and culture exchange, as well as in the fields of technical sciences and engineering. Through the Confucius Institute, students are deeply learning the Chinese language. Dual degree programs are actively functioning at TSUOS and other

universities. Every year, hundreds of Uzbek students are studying in Beijing, Shanghai, and other cities through Chinese scholarships. Relations with South Korea have significantly strengthened in recent years. The KOICA organization is supporting numerous educational projects in Uzbekistan. Relations with South Korea have significantly strengthened in recent years. The KOICA organization is supporting numerous educational projects in Uzbekistan. Bilateral degree programs have been introduced in cooperation with Korean universities. The Korean technological education model serves as an important experience school for Uzbek students and teachers. The European Union is supporting educational exchanges through programs like Erasmus+. DAAD (Germany), Campus France, and other European organizations offer grants and scholarships. Joint scientific projects and centers are active in Uzbekistan's universities in collaboration with countries such as Germany, France, and England. There is a historical, cultural, and religious closeness with Turkey, which is also reflected in the field of education. Many students are studying in Turkey through the 'Turkey Scholarships' program. Additionally, the TICA organization is actively involved in developing technical assistance and educational infrastructure. The relations with Russia, on the other hand, have deep historical roots. Students from Uzbekistan are studying in many universities in Russia. The fields of educational exchange and scientific cooperation are currently still maintained. However, there are certain restrictions regarding political factors and diplomatic recognition.

Methodology

In this research, author aimed to thoroughly study the education and development processes of Uzbekistan after independence. In total, over 20 scientific articles, government documents, reports from international organizations, and statistical data were analyzed for the research. These sources helped to better understand the changes in political, economic, and foreign relations during the periods of Karimov and Mirziyoyev. In data collection, author prioritized reliable and relevant sources. Subsequently, author analyzed the collected data in terms of quality and quantity to identify the differences and similarities in foreign policy and economic policy between the two periods. Author also reviewed previous research on the topic to compare their approaches and conclusions. By synthesizing the results of the analysis, author combined information from various sources related to the topic and formed general conclusions. During the research, the conservative and balanced policy of the Karimov era and the open and reform-based approach of the Mirziyoyev era were identified. Thus, through this research, author systematically studied the existing literature on the topic and aimed to create a scientific basis for better understanding the development processes of Uzbekistan after independence.

Discussion

Uzbekistan's foreign policy and economic development after independence underwent significant changes during the presidencies of Karimov and Mirziyoyev. In this process, Russia, China, the United States, South Korea, and Central Asian countries play an integral role as the country's main partners. Unique beneficial relationships developed with each of them, and Uzbekistan gained significant advantages in economic and social fields. During Karimov's presidency, Uzbekistan focused more on strategic and economic cooperation with Russia and China. Strong ties were established with Russia in the military and security sectors, ensuring regional stability. China became an important partner in economic investments and infrastructure projects. However, during this period, the country faced restrictions in economic openness and attracting investments. During Mirziyoyev's era, foreign policy has reached a new stage. Relations with neighboring Central Asian countries have improved, and dialogues on border and water resource issues have been intensified. The scope of international cooperation has expanded, and economic and educational ties with the United States and European countries have been developed. In the field of education, cooperation with the United States and South Korea, in particular, has brought significant benefits to the country. The scholarships provided by America, as well as student and professor exchange programs, are creating opportunities for the youth of Uzbekistan to acquire

modern knowledge and advanced scientific experiences. This is crucial for training qualified personnel and implementing innovations in the country. Cooperation with South Korea is also opening up great opportunities for Uzbekistan's youth in learning technologies and practical knowledge. Projects carried out with Korean universities serve the economic diversification of the country and the training of personnel in new sectors. Additionally, collaborations with Germany, Japan, and other developed countries in education, scientific research, and infrastructure are helping Uzbekistan to implement modern standards and become competitive on an international scale. Thus, relations with key partner countries in Uzbekistan's foreign policy not only ensure political stability but also contribute to economic growth, Uzbekistan's relations with key partner countries in its foreign policy are not only ensuring political stability but also yielding significant results in economic growth, education, and infrastructure. During the Mirziyoyev era, these processes have accelerated, strengthening the country's global integration. Analysis shows that continuing to focus on education, innovations, and international cooperation is crucial for Uzbekistan's future development. It should also be noted that the second President of Uzbekistan opened all the doors in various ways. Taken Mirziyoyev's achievements through education and sport. Near the years Uzbekistan achieved great success within sport and education with foreign countries. Taken strategic cooperation with developed countries of the world has been established in the field of education. Branches of a number of prestigious foreign universities have begun operating in Uzbekistan in cooperation with the USA, Germany, South Korea, Japan, Russia, China and other countries. In particular, Webster (USA), Inha (Korea), MISIS and MGIMO (Russia), Turin Polytechnic (Italy), Westminster (Great Britain) universities are operating. This has created an opportunity for Uzbek youth to receive international-level education and acquire modern knowledge and skills. Also, hundreds of talented young people study in foreign countries every year through international programs such as the "El-yurt Umidi" Foundation, Erasmus+, DAAD, Chevening. This serves to integrate international experience into the domestic system. Between 2021 and 2025, the volume of foreign investments in the education sector exceeded \$1 billion. These funds were directed to the development of modern training centers, vocational institutions, IT parks, and digital education infrastructure. The sports sector was also not left out of the spotlight. The state budget allocated to sports infrastructure doubled, more than 100 new sports facilities were built, and existing facilities were reconstructed. The conditions created for coaches and athletes were clearly reflected in their successes in the international arena. At the 2024 Summer Olympics in Paris, Uzbekistan achieved record results: 90 athletes participated in 19 sports, winning 8 gold, 2 silver and 3 bronze medals. This is one of the highest figures in the country's history. At the Paralympic Games, Uzbek athletes also won 26 medals, placing in the top ten. At the same time, Uzbekistan managed to qualify for the 2026 FIFA World Cup for the first time. Today, about 300 sports are being developed in Uzbekistan. Federations operate in most of them. In addition to popular sports such as football, boxing, athletics, wrestling, swimming, judo, taekwondo, less popular but internationally competitive sports such as dance sports, skiing, triathlon, paragliding, cycling, skateboarding, diving and others are also actively developing. Large sports complexes, Olympic reserve centers, and children's sports academies have been established in Tashkent, Fergana, Samarkand and other cities. In conclusion, his achievements and actions made the country stand alone independently.

Conclusion

The foreign relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan have developed radically in recent years, strengthening the country's position in the international arena. While under former President Islam Karimov, a foreign policy was mainly based on the principle of neutrality, under the leadership of the current leader Shavkat Mirziyoyev, Uzbekistan has transitioned to a more open, active and multi-directional foreign policy. This has further strengthened the country's geopolitical position and participation in regional cooperation. Under Mirziyoyev, Uzbekistan paid special attention to strengthening its good-neighborly policy with the countries of Central Asia. In this regard, new agreements were signed with Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan in the economic, transport, energy and cultural spheres. Strategic partnerships with Russia, China, and USA have also been maintained, and this cooperation is expanding, especially in the economic and educational spheres.

Cooperation with China and the USA in the field of education is strengthening, student exchange, joint programs and the activities of institutions are developing. Projects are also being developed with international organizations in the areas of English language teaching, digital education, and teacher training and advanced training. This contributes to improving the quality of education and bringing it closer to international standards. Uzbekistan's foreign policy has been developing in recent years based on openness, cooperation, and regional integration. Active cooperation with international organizations and developed countries in the field of education serves to increase the country's intellectual potential and influence in the global arena. This approach creates the basis for the sustainable development of Uzbekistan in the long term.

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